

Effect of Therapeutic Simulated Laughter on Psychological Well - Being Among Adolescents in Selected Orphanages

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Abstract-The purpose of the study is to assess the effect of Therapeutic simulated laughter on Psychological well-being among adolescents who are residing in the Orphanages. **Background:** - Laughter is believed to have a huge effect on physical as well as mental health of humans. Therefore, laughter has been developed as a therapy and practice to promote health and well-being of an Individual. Laughter Therapy is a therapy that uses humor to relieve stress and improve a sense of well-being. **Aim of the study:** To assess the effect of “Therapeutic Simulated Laughter” on Psychological well- being among Adolescents. **Methodology:-** The quasi-experimental pretest post-test only group design was used to conduct the study. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used to collect 40 samples of adolescents including girls and boys. The tool used for the study is modified Ryff’s Psychological well-being scale that was developed with the help of five -point Likert scale to collect the data. **Result:** It was observed that majority of samples 39 (97.5%) reported to have increased Psychological well-being from moderate to greater in the post test. Only 1 (2.5%) reported to have moderate Psychological well-being. None of the sample reported to have poor Psychological well-being in the post test. There is significant effect of therapeutic simulated laughter on Psychological Well-being among adolescents as P value is <0.0001. Hence H₀ is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. **Conclusion:** The study concludes Therapeutic Simulated Laughter is effective, suitable and non pharmacological technique in increasing Psychological well-being among adolescents residing in the Orphanage. Laughter therapy also improves various components of psychological well-being.

Key words: - effect, therapeutic simulated laughter, psychological well-being, adolescent, orphanage

I. INTRODUCTION

As per World Health Organization (WHO) Orphan children experience depression, mood fluctuations, lack of interest or pleasure, low energy, guilt feelings, Disruption of self-control, lack of sleep, decrease appetite, lack of concentration. The prevalence of orphaned youth depression was 36.4% with physical ailments such as digestive problems, insomnia, boredom or helplessness, and social isolation that affect interpersonal relationships which lead to the development of their personality, Strong negative emotions, poor self-image, low self-confidence, increased daily stress, poor internal and external stress management, psychological problems, impairments in creative activities, and cognitive demotivation are consequences of poor communication . Orphans were found to have low levels of spiritual well-being, while non-orphans had high levels of spiritual well-being. Orphans who receive educational support may delay the onset or severity of depression symptoms. A parent's illness or death impacts every aspect of a child's life, and it typically marks the beginning of significant changes. Parental death and illness are traumatic childhood occurrences linked to various physical and mental health problems.

According to studies, adolescents in orphanages are more likely to develop emotional illnesses like anxiety, despair, and stress. Adolescents with good mental health can identify their skills, manage daily stress, and contribute to their communities.

Orphans in orphanages face a world, where they must go about their daily lives without receiving appropriate attention from their caretakers. As a result, orphaned adolescents are more likely to experience emotional and behavioral problems such as depression, social inhibition, loneliness. Although the processes may differ, the high prevalence of mental health disorders, primarily emotional problems, appears similar to studies of other neglected, traumatized, and institutionalized children. The loss of a parent as a youngster causes a slew of psychological and emotional issues. They are in danger of anxiousness due to a lack of self-determination and incapacity to make decisions, impacting their performance. According to the Integrated Child Protection Program, children and adolescents who grew up in institutions in India who are orphans, runaways, or abandoned by their relatives are among the most vulnerable groups (ICPS) (MWCD, 2018). According to the research, behavioral and emotional disorders affect 18.3% to 64.53% of orphans and other vulnerable adolescents due to abuse, exploitation, neglect, and lack of parental love and care, were observed to be between 8.7 percent and 18.7 percent; Orphans and other children at risk are more prone to emotional and behavioral problems. They're also more emotionally dependent, insecure, and deprived. Aside from these issues, most children are reared in institutions where they receive insufficient individual attention. These variables can negatively impact young children's social and emotional development. Emotional and behavioral issues impact child's overall development, particularly intellectual and social consequences as an adult.

Therefore, mental health promotion interventions may help an adolescent to strengthen their capacity to regulate emotions, reduce risk-taking behaviors, build resilience for managing difficult situations and promote supportive, social environments and psychological well-being.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Effect of Therapeutic Simulated Laughter on Psychological Well - Being Among Adolescents in Selected Orphanages.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the effect of "Therapeutic Simulated Laughter" on Psychological well-being among Adolescents.

IV. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Therapeutic simulated laughter:-It refers to a therapy that includes, greeting laughter, national lottery laughter, hot soup laughter, lion laughter, cell phone laughter, argument laughter, electric shock laughter and it will be administered 30 minutes a day for 7 consecutive days.

V. HYPOTHESIS

H0- There will be no effect of Therapeutic simulated Laughter on Psychological well-being among adolescents in selected Orphanages.

H1- There will be a significant effect of Therapeutic simulated Laughter on Psychological well-being among adolescents in selected Orphanages.

VI. ASSUMPTION

1. Adolescents residing at Orphanages have poor Psychological well-being.
2. Therapeutic simulated Laughter will improve Psychological well-being of adolescents residing in the Orphanages.

VII. ETHICAL ASPECTS

1. The study proposal has sanctioned by the institutional ethical committee of college.
2. Official permission is obtained from concerned authorities of selected Orphanages.
3. Verbal consent is taken from all the participants. (Minors-12yrs to 18yrs)
4. Informed written consent is taken from the legally authorized representative of selected Orphanages.
5. Confidentiality of data is ensured.

VIII. RESEARCH DESIGN

The researcher has adopted quasi experimental (one group) pretest post-test only group design to assess the effect of therapeutic simulated laughter on psychological well-being among adolescents in selected Orphanages. The study has been conducted in the selected Orphanages in which adolescents including girls and boys between the age group of 12 years to 18 years are residing. The Orphanage is selected based on administrative support, co-operation, availability of samples and convenience for transportation.

A. Inclusion criteria

1. Adolescents who are in the age group of 12-18yrs.
2. Adolescents those who are willing to participate in the study.
3. Those who are able to read English and Marathi.
4. Both boys and girls will be included in the study.

B. Exclusion criteria

1. Adolescents who are physically and mentally challenged.
2. Those who are having congenital anomaly of face.
3. Those who have undergone recent abdominal surgery.

C. Description of the Tool-

Section A:- Modified Ryff's Psychological well-being scale was developed to collect data from the participants. Five-point Likert scale was developed, the modified tool consists of 20 items. The item assesses the level of psychological well-being of adolescents residing in the selected Orphanages. Each item scores strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4) and strongly agree (5). The maximum score is 100 whereas the minimum score is 20.

Scoring interpretation: The scoring system is divided into following categories.

- 74-100 - Greater Psychological well-being
- 47-73- Moderate Psychological well-being
- 20-46- Poor Psychological well-being

D. Method of Data Collection:

Permission from concerned authorities: -Prior to collection of data, permission was obtained from legally authorized representative of the selected Orphanage.

Period of data collection:-The data collection was done in the month of May 2024. After taking official permission from legally authorized representative of the selected Orphanage. Verbal consent is also taken from each participant. Dates were planned. Each participant in the study was explained about the purpose and importance of the study.

Process of data collection:-The participants were selected as per the led down criteria. The nature of the study was briefly explained and it was ensured that samples who are willing to participate in the study were only included.

Pre-test: Modified Ryff's Psychological well-being scale was given to participants along with the pretest on Psychological well-being. (Day 1)

Intervention: Therapeutic simulated Laughter for 30 min for 7 days (Day 2 to day 8)

Post-test: Post-test was taken on 9th day as per planned schedule

E. Plan of data Analysis

The data analysis was planned to include descriptive and inferential statistics and present them in the form of tables, graphs and figures. The data was entered in MS excel file and analysis was done by using SPSS (Statistical package for the social science) version 23. Tests used such as Wilcoxon, Mann Whitney test and Fisher's exact test.

IX RESULT

Section I: -Description on Assessment of Psychological Well-being among Adolescents Residing at Selected Orphanage

TABLE I
ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG ADOLESCENTS

n=40

Psychological well-being	Pre test (%)	Post test (%)
20 – 46 (Poor)	0	0
47 – 73 (Moderate)	33 (82.5)	1 (2.5)
74 – 100 (Greater)	7 (17.5)	39 (97.5)
Total	40 (100)	40 (100)

- Table I shows Majority of samples 33 (82.5%) have moderate Psychological well-being in the pretest, whereas 7 (17.5%) reported to have greater psychological well-being. None of the sample reported to have poor Psychological well-being.
- After the intervention, majority of samples 39 (97.5%) reported to have increased Psychological well-being from moderate to greater in the post test. Only 1 (2.5%) reported to have moderate Psychological well-being. None of the sample reported to have poor Psychological well-being in the post test.

Section II: Analysis on Area Wise Effect of Therapeutic Simulated Laughter on Psychological Well-being Among Adolescents

TABLE II
AREA WISE EFFECT OF THERAPEUTIC SIMULATED LAUGHTER ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

n=40

Area of Psychological well-being	Pre test		Post test		Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Self -acceptance	13.98	2.11	17.78	1.51	5.24	<0.0001	27.18
Positive relationship with others	10.35	2.78	16.48	2.06	5.23	<0.0001	59.23
Autonomy	12.53	2.80	17.43	1.71	5.33	<0.0001	39.11
Life development	15.05	2.01	17.93	1.44	5.10	<0.0001	19.14
Emotional well-being	14.60	2.08	17.68	1.80	5.20	<0.0001	21.10

GRAPH I
AREA WISE EFFECT OF THERAPEUTIC SIMULATED LAUGHTER ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

Table II and Graph I shows that there is area wise effect of Therapeutic simulated Laughter on Psychological Well-being among adolescents as P value is <0.0001. Positive relationship with others and autonomy shows significant more difference in posttest mean value compare to other components of Psychological well-being. Hence H₀ is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Section III: -Description on Effect of Therapeutic Simulated Laughter on Psychological Well-being Among Adolescents

TABLE III

EFFECT OF THERAPEUTIC SIMULATED LAUGHTER ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG ADOLESCENTS

n=40

Parameter	Pre test		Post test		Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Psychological well-being	66.50	8.051	87.28	5.570	5.49	<0.0001	31.25

Percentage change = 31.25%

GRAPH II

EFFECT OF THERAPEUTIC SIMULATED LAUGHTER ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG ADOLESCENTS

Table III and Graph II shows that the mean value of Psychological well-being in the pretest was 66.50 and post-test was 87.28, which shows there is significant effect of Therapeutic simulated laughter on Psychological Well-being among adolescents as P value is <0.0001. Hence H₀ is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

X. DISCUSSION

A) The study findings was consistent with the study done by Ozturk, F.O., &Acikgoz, I. (2022)

The finding of the study showed that there was a significant difference on the level of happiness ($p < .05$) in the experimental group compared to the control group. The study further

recommends to organize laughter therapy activities in schools to increase the happiness levels of students. The current study supports the findings of this study as it was observed that therapeutic simulated laughter is significantly effective in increasing the psychological well-being among adolescents as P value is <0.0001 .

B) The study findings was consistent with the study done by Katharina Stiwi, Jenny Rosendahl (2022)

The findings of the study showed that Laughter-inducing interventions have significant positive effects on mental health (31 studies, 1,543 patients, $g = 0.74$, 95% CI [0.48; 1.00], $I^2 = 81\%$), physiological (14 studies, 761 patients, $g = 0.61$ [0.20; 1.03], $I^2 = 86\%$), and physical health outcomes (21 studies, 1,105 patients, $g = 0.59$ [0.30; 0.88], $I^2 = 80\%$). The study further recommends that Laughter-inducing interventions might benefit patients to improve mood, well-being, quality of life, reduced anxiety, depression, stress, pain or fatigue. The current study supports the findings of this study. The current study supports the findings of this study as it was observed that therapeutic simulated laughter is significantly effective in increasing the psychological well-being as P value is <0.0001 .

C) The study findings was consistent with the study done by Selene Robena Illner (2019)

Quasi-experimental study was conducted on Laughter Yoga- a Positive Psychology Intervention. The study reported that participants in the Laughter Yoga group showed significant increased of emotional well-being ($p < 0.01$) as well as mood ($p < 0.001$) of the participants compared to the control group. The study further concluded that Laughter Yoga is a suitable positive, psychological intervention to enhance mental well-being of an Individual. The current study supports the findings of this study as it was observed that therapeutic simulated laughter is significantly effective in increasing psychological well-being as P value is <0.0001 .

XI. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was limited to selected Orphanage.
- The study is limited to the adolescents (12 years to 18 years) in the selected Orphanage

XII. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. This study can be performed on larger population to generalize the findings.
2. An exploratory study can be done to assess various problems and issues faced by the Orphan children.
3. A similar study can be conducted in Old age home along with play therapy or recreational activities.
4. A similar study can be done to assess the effect of laughter therapy on emotional and physiological well-being of school children.

XIII. CONCLUSION

The result of this study revealed that the adolescents who received therapeutic simulated laughter had a statistically significant improvement in psychological well-being. Therefore therapeutic simulated laughter is highly recommended because it is non-pharmacological and cost effective technique to improve psychological well-being of adolescents residing in the Orphanage.

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